

Review of the Functioning of Pharmaceutical Marketing in the Context of New Social Media Techniques

Tejashree Kamath & Dr. Prabhakar Neermarga
Research Scholar, Institute of Management & Commerce,
Srinivas University, Mangalore- 575001, India

Abstract:-

Purpose: The main aim of this study is to appraise of functioning of pharmaceutical marketing in the context of new social media techniques.

Methodology: The researcher has used “primary quantitative data gathering tool” to gather fresh, authentic, and first-hand data and “SPSS Software” to explore the information in an understandable way.

Findings: Nowadays social media has been identified as one of the effective mediums for marketing and businesses. Pharmaceutical companies are using new social media techniques to market drugs and medical devices to secure growth positively. In order to manage waste and provide betterment, it has a great impact.

Value: The study discusses the beneficial sites as well as disadvantages of current pharmaceutical marketing with the collaboration of new social media techniques which assist in enhancing the value of the paper with future scope.

Keywords:- Pharmaceutical marketing, social media techniques, development, customers.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background of the study

The revolution in social media techniques is pressurizing the “retail pharmacy production” to establish new business versions to gain functional excellence. Accompanied by the rapid transformation, social media has transformed the paths to prepare a new world of chances and challenges for all perspectives of the pharmaceutical marketing process.

B. Aims and objectives

In this research, the researcher has set a few research objectives to lead this study toward a conclusion. The objectives are:

- To understand the functions of Pharmaceutical Marketing
- To evaluate the perspectives on the utilisation of social media in e-pharma marketing
- To analyse the role and experience of social media techniques in Pharmaceutical Marketing

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Functioning of Pharmaceutical Marketing

Pharmaceutical Marketing develops brands for marketing of the pharmaceutical company creating brand strategies, promoting the brand, target customers and segmentation of the company, as well as creating a chart of expenses for the brand. Pharmaceutical marketing is very important as many Doctors rely on pharma companies to get updates about medicines and diseases (Wenny, 2020). This marketing transfer’s knowledge and information about medicines to doctors, based on the information doctors can make clinical decisions and therapies for the patients if needed. This marketing strategy helps the brand to reach the business goals of the pharma company on a higher level.

B. Perspectives for the Use of Social Media in e-Pharma Marketing

Social media is one of the most important platforms for today’s generation; however, there are positive and negative impacts of social media. Today, inspired by social media, people are trying self-medication but this anyhow affects the relationship between patients and physicians (Mukherjee et al., 2021). Consumers get access to a lot of resources and applications through the use of fast-spreading internet and social media platforms, as pharmaceutical companies advertise their brands on different social media platforms (Mekawie & Hany, 2019). The recent outbreak of “The COVID-19” virus prompted almost all pharma companies to turn their marketing online and the pharmaceutical business is very essential for every human being throughout the world (Dcruz, 2022).

Pharmaceutical companies and firms are constantly facing problems as the competition in the market is increasing every day. These companies and firms have tried many new innovative ideas to promote their businesses to the consumers, however, the leading brands are focusing on marketing strategies rather than research and acknowledgement (Costa, Tiago, & Tiago, 2018). The world is evolving every day and so are businesses, and today everything and every piece of information are available on social media platforms which are increasing the competition in the pharmaceutical market day by day.

C. Role and Experience of Social Media in Pharmaceutical Marketing

Pharmaceutical firms and companies are increasing their use of social media for marketing their brand and their products to consumers. Pharmaceutical industries and shippers spend millions of rupees these days promoting their brands through every social media platform (Mukherjee, Kumar, & Jha, 2021). More than 40% of people trust the information shared on social media about health choices and 90% of social media users in the age group of “18 to 24 years old” rely on social media more and prefer to discuss their health issues online. Nowadays, it is impossible to ignore the impact of social media; however, social media marketing has its own rules and regulations, which is quite challenging and difficult as the competition in online marketing is increasing day by day (Pharmaceutical Technology, 2021).

There are challenges in pharmaceutical marketing such as targeting consumers and reaching the goals, providing true and best information to the consumers, building the trust of the consumers, keeping a track record of the progress and maintaining the regulations of online healthcare marketing. However, there are sometimes, misinformation spreads on social media and all pharmaceutical brands should be more attentive to the factors in decreasing the misinformation from the internet and social media platforms. Most people rely on the internet and find it much safer from their emotional perspectives, to get rid of feeling misjudged by others and sometimes even by family members.

D. Theoretical perspective

Social selling and interaction theory is a theory which helps businesses, brands and firms to build a two-way and transparent relationship between the company and the consumers. Also, this theory helps the brands or the companies to interact with the consumers, individually and helps to understand consumers issues more clearly. Implementing this theory in pharmaceutical marketing will support the business in increasing its position in the market. It will help in collecting data on different issues of the consumers, as well as the brands can communicate with their customers directly. Implementing the theory in the business will help to gain the trust of the consumers, as it

will engage the consumers individually with the brand and the relationship with the company will be strong which will increase the rate of selling products to their customers as social media is a larger platform to target consumers (Shawky et al., 2019). Automatically it will gain more customers' attention which will increase the productivity of the companies, brands and firms.

E. Literature gap

This study has been conducted depending on the primary quantitative data; hence, the main gap of this article is associated with the lack of secondary qualitative data which could have helped in evaluating the topic of pharmaceutical marketing more effectively. The other gaps in this article are associated lack of word count which have decreased the level of evaluating the topic more effectively.

III. METHODS

Methodology is one of the crucial parts in any research process and in this purpose the researcher has chosen all the tools for leading this particular research topic conscientiously. The **“positivism research philosophy”** has been selected by the researcher as it is highly structured and able to control large-size data (Park, Konge, & Artino, 2020). In addition, the research also can be free from the study and there are no provisions for human interest within the research. The **“inductive research approach”** has helped the developer to prepare a useful outcome to bring a conclusion dependent on a clear examination. In addition to this, a **“descriptive research design”** has been selected by the researcher to collect the data as it is depending on all the aspects that can be evaluated perfectly. In order to measure the information and recognising it in a better way, this research tool has been proved very useful.

Along with this, the **“primary quantitative data gathering tool”** has also assisted the researcher to draw out all the interconnected data and information related to the investigation topic. It is useful as it serves first-hand raw data that is able to make the research valuable. A survey questionnaire has been prepared as well as a population sample of **30 participants** has been chosen to conduct the research process. In addition, a statistical analysis using **IBM software** has been selected to analyse the primary data.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
How would you rate your overall experience with online marketing experience?	30	0	5	3.67	1.155
Satisfied with range of medicine available online	30	0	3	.57	.935
Quality and Condition of medicine	30	0	3	.53	.937
Overall your ratings for social media marketing in the pharmaceutical sector	30	0	5	3.30	1.208
Valid N (listwise)	30				

Fig. 1: Descriptive statistics

(Source: SPSS)

Descriptive statistics are used for evaluating the findings meaningfully and descriptively. The mean values of the variables are a major part of descriptive statistics which evaluates the average of the findings (Mishra et al. 2019). The calculated mean values of the specific variables of this

study are **3.67, 0.57, 0.53, and 3.30**. Apart from that, the standard deviation values of all the variables are **1.155, 0.935, 0.937, and 1.208**. All the values are not larger than 1 which indicates that the responses remained positive as well as negative regarding all the questions in the survey.

Correlations					
		How would you rate your overall experience with online marketing experience?	Satisfied with range of medicine available online	Quality and Condition of medicine	Overall your ratings for social media marketing in the pharmaceutical sector
How would you rate your overall experience with online marketing experience?	Pearson Correlation	1	-.106	-.117	.791**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.576	.539	.000
	N	30	30	30	30
Satisfied with range of medicine available online	Pearson Correlation	-.106	1	.942**	-.095
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.576		.000	.619
	N	30	30	30	30
Quality and Condition of medicine	Pearson Correlation	-.117	.942**	1	-.146
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.539	.000		.441
	N	30	30	30	30
Overall your ratings for social media marketing in the pharmaceutical sector	Pearson Correlation	.791**	-.095	-.146	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.619	.441	
	N	30	30	30	30

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Fig. 2: Correlation statistics

(Source: SPSS)

Correlation statistics are also an important part of statistical analysis which is a process of identifying the type of relationship among the variables of a study. According to the rules, if the “significance values” are less than 0.05 then it reveals that there is a positive relation whereas if the “significance values” are more than 0.05 then it reveals that

there is a negative relationship among the variables (Akoglu, 2018). In the above table, the significance value is 0 for all the variables which are lower than 0.05 and that reveals that there is a positive relationship among all the variables in this study.

Fig. 3: Age group

(Source: SPSS)

In the survey, there was the lowest age was 19 years and the highest age was 74 years among all 30 participants.

20% was the highest percentage that belongs between 20 and 21 years of age and the lowest ratio was 3.33%.

Fig. 4: Profession

(Source: SPSS)

There were participated a total of 30 participants from different professional backgrounds. The largest ratio of 36.67% student patients, 20% were pharmacist patients,

6.67% were doctors, and 3.33% were the remaining professionals patients.

Fig. 5: How do you make arrangements for your medical needs

(Source: SPSS)

In the first question, 56.67% of the participants answered that doctors make arrangements for their medical needs. On the contrary, 43.33% of the participants answered

those medical store make arrangements for their medical needs.

Fig. 6: Are you using social media marketing for pharmaceutical purposes

(Source: SPSS)

According to the above graph, regarding the purpose of using social media marketing for pharmaceuticals, 40% of participants agreed and 60% of participants did not agree.

The majority of people are not using social media for pharmaceutical purpose.

Fig. 7: Which social media you are using for medicine purposes

(Source: SPSS)

Based on the above graph, 16.67% of participants mentioned that they did not use any kind of social media for medicine purposes. In addition, 13.33% of participants answered they are using the medical store to purchase

medicines. Thus, 6.67% of participants used Netmeds, Needy, and Google, and 3.33% of participants used other social media platforms.

Fig. 8: Satisfied with the range of medicine available online

(Source: SPSS)

Among the available medicines online, 66.67% of the participants have satisfied and 16.67% of participants were very satisfied with them. Thus, 10% of the participants have unsatisfied and 6.67% of the participants were very unsatisfied with it.

Fig. 9: Easy to find your need

(Source: SPSS)

There are 80% of respondents are agreed that they can find easily the required medicines online. On the contrary, 20% of respondents have mentioned they have found this process as tough.

Fig. 10: Quality and condition of medicine

(Source: SPSS)

According to the survey, 70% of respondents are satisfied and 13.33% of respondents are very satisfied with the quality and condition of medicine available online. On the opposite side, 10% of respondents are unsatisfied and 6.67% of respondents are very unsatisfied with this.

Fig. 11: Overall your ratings for social media marketing in the pharmaceutical sector

(Source: SPSS)

The largest 36.67% of respondents have given a rating of 3 to the “social media marketing” in the pharmaceutical sector and the lowest rating was 3.33% based on 0 and 1.

Fig. 12: Do you feel in the future there will be more demand for online marketing for medicine purpose

(Source: SPSS)

There were **86.67%** of participants agreed and **13.33%** of participants did not agree with this statement.

Fig. 13: Do you feel there is any advantage of social media marketing in the pharmaceutical sector

(Source: SPSS)

There were **83.33%** of participants agreed and **13.33%** of participants did not agree with this statement.

B. Discussion

The majority of people are satisfied with pharmaceutical stores rather than social media platforms to purchase medicines. Thus, there is a great opportunity for social media platforms to secure the approach in the future.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusion

Pharmacists believe that social media can modify the quality of customers (patients) as well as increase the number options for purchasing and selling medicines. Social media techniques are able to develop the annual revenue of pharmaceutical marketing process. In this context, pharmaceutical firms and companies are increasing their use of social media for marketing their brand and their products to consumers. This marketing strategy helps the brand to reach the business goals of the pharma company on a higher level.

B. Suggestions

Adoption of modern and new technologies can make sure the pharmaceutical marketing process will gain profits. In addition, new internet technologies also can prove as useful to enhance the availability of medicines at any place at any time. Technological approach will be resulted great in the case of increasing peoples’ awareness about online platform. In addition to that, using social media platforms can develop better interaction among Pharmaceutical companies, doctors as well as patients currently. This approach is of prime importance in light of cost effectiveness for both manufacturers, dealers, doctors and patients too. Moreover in the interest of consumer and ever dealers use of social media can give them information about the same drug or medicine manufactured by different companies with respect to quality and price.

Pharmaceutical marketing must be a steady and sustained effort to be successful and achieve profit margin. Besides this, team members must be motivated and encouraged to send relevant information on the social media platforms, this will help in maintaining healthy relationship with Pharmaceutical companies, doctors as well as patients

REFERENCES

- [1.] Akoglu, H. (2018). User's guide to correlation coefficients. *Turkish journal of emergency medicine*, 18(3), 91-93. Retrieved on: 6th December, 2022, Retrieved from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2452247318302164>
- [2.] Costa, T., Tiago, B. T., & Tiago, F., (2018). Pharmaceutical Communication over Social Media Channels: 24/7 Management Challenges. *Digital Communication Management*. Retrieved on: 6th December, 2022, Retrieved from: <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/61015>
- [3.] Dcruz, A. C., Mokashi, V. N., Pai, S. R., & Sreedhar, D. (2022). The rise of E-pharmacy in India: Benefits, challenges, and the road ahead. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*, 54(4), 282. Retrieved from: <https://ijp-online.com/article.asp?issn=0253-7613;year=2022;volume=54;issue=4;spage=282;epage=291;aulast=Dcruz>
- [4.] Mekawie, N., & Hany, A. (2019). Understanding the factors driving consumers' purchase intention of over the counter medications using social media advertising in Egypt:(A Facebook advertising application for cold and Flu products). *Procedia Computer Science*, 164, 698-705. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2019.12.238>
- [5.] Mishra, P., Pandey, C. M., Singh, U., Gupta, A., Sahu, C., & Keshri, A. (2019). Descriptive statistics and normality tests for statistical data. *Annals of cardiac anaesthesia*, 22(1), 67. Retrieved on: 6th December, 2022, Retrieved from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6350423/>
- [6.] Mukherjee, S. K., Kumar, J., & Jha, A. (2021). Impact of Social Media Promotion on Pharmaceutical Organizations. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 3315-3322. Retrieved from: <https://www.annalsofrscb.ro/index.php/journal/article/view/1820/1522>
- [7.] Mukherjee, S., Pandey, V., Kumar, J., & Jha, A. (2021). A Study of User Profile and Their Attitudes about Social Media Promotion of Prescription Drugs in Eastern India. Available at SSRN 3988821. Retrieved from: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3988821
- [8.] Park, Y. S., Konge, L., & Artino, A. R. (2020). The positivism paradigm of research. *Academic Medicine*, 95(5), 690-694. Retrieved on: 6th December, 2022, Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0000000000003093>
- [9.] Pharmaceutical Technology, 2021. *Logging in: how the pharma industry is getting to grips with social media*. Retrieved on: 6th December, 2022, Retrieved from: <https://www.pharmaceutical-technology.com/features/pharma-social-media-marketing/>
- [10.] Shawky, S., Kubacki, K., Dietrich, T., & Weaven, S. (2019). Using social media to create engagement: A social marketing review. *Journal of Social Marketing*. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSOCM-05-2018-0046>
- [11.] Wenny, 2020. Pharma Function Highlights: Pharmaceutical Marketing and Smruti Ghag. *Women in Pharma Careers*, Retrieved on: 6th December, 2022, Retrieved from: [https://womeninpharmacareers.com/pharma-function-highlights-pharmaceutical-marketing-and-smruti-ghag/#:~:text=Marketing%20is%20responsible%20for%20developing,as%20expenses\)%20for%20every%20brand.](https://womeninpharmacareers.com/pharma-function-highlights-pharmaceutical-marketing-and-smruti-ghag/#:~:text=Marketing%20is%20responsible%20for%20developing,as%20expenses)%20for%20every%20brand.)